

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Environmental technology verification (ETV)

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is an outcome of Subtask 7.2.3, the aim of which is to validate the environmental performance and claims of ECOBULK solutions through the Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) scheme. The objective of an ETV is to promote environmental technologies by providing technology developers, manufacturers and investors access to third-party validation of the performance of innovative environmental technologies.

This deliverable has been provided in two versions, the initial version at M32 and this final version. This version includes the initial version introducing the ETV tool and verification process, Accredited ETV Verification Bodies and the process of selecting them for ECOBULK, as well as the main characteristics of the ECOBULK technology being proposed for ETV.

Technology proposed for ETV is Conenor's Agglomeration process for manufacturing raw materials from recycled and waste feedstock materials; and extruded single- and multilayer products (e.g. planks and panels) thereof for the construction industry. The technology has been proposed for ETV due to its ability of recycling complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) by manufacturing into new circular raw materials to improve the materials efficiency, as well as their sustainability. A first form was filled in, in order to collect information about the technology proposed to verification in order to evaluate whether it is eligible for verification under the EU ETV Programme and to provide a first indication of the costs involved. The result of this process was successful but for financial and technical reasons, the process did not go on to the next step. Technically speaking, since Conenor is a research & development centre with pilot scale equipment only, the technology needs to be implemented at an industrial level to submit a file to the ETV Programme to become verified in due course at real manufacturing conditions and adequate representative up-scaled equipment at a Conenor client having acquired a license from Conenor. Currently this is not yet existing.

However, ETV is not the only solution to valorise what has been developed by the company. Environmental Production Declaration is an independently verified and registered document that communicates transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. Benchmark of different EPD database show very few cladding solutions involving the recycling of post-consumer waste. EPD appears to be a solution to valorise the environmental performance of the composite products developed by Conenor.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable is an outcome of Subtask 7.2.3, the aim of which is to validate the environmental performance and claims of ECOBULK solutions through the Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) scheme. The objective of an ETV is to promote environmental technologies by providing technology developers, manufacturers and investors access to third-party validation of the performance of innovative environmental technologies.

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However, ETV is not the only solution to valorise what has been developed by the company. Environmental Production Declaration is an independently verified and registered document that communicates transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. Benchmark of different EPD database show very few cladding solutions involving the recycling of post-consumer waste. EPD appears to be a solution to valorise the environmental performance of the composite products developed by Conenor.

2. Introduction to Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) tool

The problem of innovative technologies providing solutions to environmental problems can face difficulties in penetrating the market due to lack of independent and credible evidence of its advantages. On the other hand, technology purchasers or investors committed to finding the best solution for their situation are often faced with non-comparable, incomplete or non-

trustworthy performance information when assessing the available choices on the market.¹

The concept of the Environmental Technology Verification programme is to offer a verification procedure to cutting edge environmental technologies that may otherwise find it difficult to establish their environmental added value. The verification procedure allows for an independent assessment and validation of the manufacturer's claims on the performance and environmental benefits of their technology. The information produced by the verification is public and can be used to compare performance parameters and therefore becomes an extremely useful tool to convince third-parties of the merits of a technology, potentially enhancing its market value and acceptance.

ETV is neither a label nor a certification scheme; it ensures that the claims are as structured and complete as possible so as to present a clear assessment of the entire technology's potential and value, but it does not evaluate the technology's performance against standard or pre-defined criteria. The information provided, in the form of a Statement of Verification, gives the possibility for direct and objective comparison between different technologies reducing the risk on adopting new technologies and encouraging informed and sound investments. ETV results could be used to prove compliance with any relevant legislation, to underpin a bid in public tendering, to convince investors or customers of the reliability of performance claims and to avoid having to repeat demonstrations for different users.

The verification process incorporates the key procedures of the ETV provided in Clause 5 of ISO 14034 and follows the general principles and requirements provided in Clause 4 of ISO 14034. The process itself is divided in a few (sequential) steps or phases, which is shown in Figure 1.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/etv/about-etv_en

Figure 1 Steps of ETV verification procedure²

Contact phase: The starting point for verification is a contact between the proposer and a Verification Body. Before sending a full proposal for verification, the proposer first provides a quick scan document outlining the main characteristics of the technology to be verified, following the template provided in Appendix 3 in the European Commission guiding document³. The aim of the quick scan is to enable the Verification Body to make an initial assessment of the eligibility of the technology for verification under EU ETV Pilot Programme and to give an early indication of the complexity and potential range of costs of a full verification. Where appropriate, the Verification Body provides advice on the drafting and completeness of the quick scan.

Proposal phase: After the contact phase, if the technology is potentially eligible and if the proposer decides to perform the verification, the second step is the proposal phase. The proposer provides the information needed by the Verification Body to conclude a verification contract and, under the following step, draft the specific verification protocol. The proposer submits a proposal for verification to the Verification Body, following the template

² European Commission, 2014. EU Environmental Technology Verification pilot programme Version 1.1 – July 7th, 2014 General Verification Protocol, available at:

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/etv/publications_en

³ European Commission, 2018. Environmental Technology Verification pilot programme – Version 1.3, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/environment/ecoap/etv/publications_en

provided in Appendix 4 in the European Commission guiding document⁴. At this stage, if the proposer decides to proceed, the Verification Body provides a detailed cost estimate for the verification procedure (excluding tests) together with a list of potential tests and/or analyses to be performed

Specific verification protocol phase: Upon successful completion of the contact phase and proposal phase the next steps in the process are related to the establishment of the specific verification protocol. The specific verification protocol explains how the verification is to be conducted, including a definition of the parameters covered by the verification and all relevant requirements on tests and test data (e.g. test method selection, test design, test data quality, test data assessment, etc.).

Testing including test plan: After completion of the specific verification protocol preparation phase and if additional tests are needed, the testing phase is entered into. The testing phase corresponds to and complements ISO 14034, Section 5.4.3 'Generation of additional test data'. Steps to be undertaken as part of the testing phase are: test site selection, test plan, testing and test report.

Assessment of all data and verification of performance: Upon completion of the testing phase and the collection of all relevant data, the verification body proceeds with the assessment and verification phase. The assessment and verification phase corresponds to and complements ISO 14034, Section 5.4.4 'Confirmation of performance'. This consists of several steps: test report review, conclusion of the test system assessment; assessment of all test data and verification.

Reporting and publication phase: Based on the outcome of the assessment of test data and verification, and provided that the verification procedure is not interrupted by the proposer or the Verification Body, the next phase includes drafting the Verification report, drafting the Statement of Verification and publication of the Statement of Verification.

3. ETV first round evaluation

3.1. Selection of verification body for ECOBULK project

A Verification Body is an organisation accredited as fulfilling the requirements of ISO 17020 to perform verifications under the EU ETV Pilot Programme and complying to the requirements specified in the General Verification Protocol document. Each Verification Body is accredited for at least one subset of the specific technological areas included in the ETV pilot programme: "Water Treatment and Monitoring", "Energy Technologies" or "Materials, Waste and Resources". The list of accredited verification bodies is in Table 1.

Table 1 Accredited verification bodies for the ETV programme

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Start: 01/06/2017 - End: 31/05/2021

ECOBULK

Title	Status	Accreditation Scope	Contact
BRE Global (GB)	Accredited by The United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials, Waste & Resources Energy Technologies 	John Holden etv@bregroup.com
Certiquality (IT)	Accredited by Accredia - Italian Accreditation Body	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Sabrina Melandri S.Melandri@certiquality.it
CSTB (FR)	Accredited by French Accreditation Committee (COFRAC) on 15/03/2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Water Treatment & Monitoring 	NGUYEN Coralie etv@cstb.fr
Environmental Technology Verification Body - Institute for Ecology of Industrial Areas (PL)	Accredited by Polish Centre for Accreditation (PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Izabela Ratman - Kłosińska i.ratman-klosinska@ietu.pl
ETA-Danmark (DK)	Accredited by DANAK - The Danish Accreditation and Metrology Fund	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Thomas Bruun tb@etadanmark.dk
EUROFINS EXPERT SERVICES OY (formerly VTT) (FI)	Accredited by FINAS - Finnish Accreditation Service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Matti Lanu MattiLanu@eurofins.fi
Institute of Environmental Protection - National Research Institute (IOS-PIB) (PL)	Accredited by Polish Centre for Accreditation (PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of heat and power from renewable sources of energy: wind, hydro, geothermal, biomass, solar, biogas Energy efficiency technologies: micro-turbines, hydrogen and fuel cells, heat pumps, combined heat and power, logistics, storage and recovery of energy Recycling of batteries, accumulators and chemicals Recycling of industrial by-products and waste into secondary materials Reuse of energy from waste: fuel from waste, combustion technologies Recycling of construction waste into building materials 	Bartosz Malowaniec bartosz.malowaniec@ios.edu.pl etv@ios.edu.pl

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separation or sorting techniques for solid waste, materials recovery 	
<u>Institute of Technology and Life Sciences (ITP) (PL)</u>	Accredited by Polish Centre for Accreditation (PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Products made of biomass Recycling of industrial by-products and waste into secondary materials Separation or sorting techniques for solid waste, materials recovery Recycling of construction waste into building materials Production of heat and power from renewable sources of energy: wind (wind turbines), hydro (power plants and turbines), geothermal (heat pumps, ground heat exchangers, heat recovery unit), biomass, solar (collectors, accumulators, photovoltaic cells) 	Agnieszka Wawrzyniak a.wawrzyniak@itp.edu.pl
<u>PIMOT (PL)</u>	Accredited by Polish Centre for Accreditation (PCA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials, waste and resources: Products made from biomass (bioplastics, biofuels) Energy technologies: Production of electricity and heat from renewable sources (biomass) Energy technologies: The use of energy from waste (Fuel 3rd generation) 	Roman Nadratowski r.nadratowski@pimot.eu
<u>RESCOLL (FR)</u>	Accredited by French Accreditation Committee (COFRAC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Sandrine Ausset sandrine.ausset@rescoll.fr etv@rescoll.eu
<u>RINA Services (IT)</u>	Accredited by Accredia - Italian Accreditation Body	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Giovanni D'Angelo giovanni.dangelo@rina.org Laura Severino laura.severino@rina.org
<u>The Czech Environment Management Center (CEMC) (CZ)</u>	Accredited by Czech Accreditation Institute (CAI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	Vladimír Študent studentv@cemc.cz
<u>French National Laboratory for Metrology and Testing (LNE) (Accreditation expired) (FR)</u>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies Materials, Waste & Resources Water Treatment & Monitoring 	... etv@lne.fr
<u>National Physical Laboratory</u>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technologies 	... etv@npl.co.uk

(NPL)
(Accreditation
expired) (GB)

Considering that the Verification Body cannot be part of the ECOBULK consortium, this task has been foreseen for subcontracting in the DoA. Following the rules of implementation of action tasks by subcontractors (see Art 13 of the Horizon 2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement⁴), the beneficiaries must award the subcontracts ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price. In doing so, they must avoid any conflict of interests.

No specific quality criteria have been defined for the selection of Verification Body; therefore, the subcontract will be awarded to the company that meets the conditions and quotes the lowest price. Three companies in the area of "Materials, Waste and Resources" were contacted (RINA Services, EUROFINS EXPERT SERVICES OY, RESCOLL) to initiate the process.

3.2. ECOBULK technology selected for ETV

Conenor, with the cooperation with Virol (wind turbine blade recycling company), has developed a new composite material made of wind turbine blade Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) waste. This is a first time ever when GFRP-waste is being recycled and used as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites. Complex polymeric waste, such as fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) are first shredded down mechanically into smaller particle and thereafter used in Conenor's invented and **patented agglomeration technique in Europe, USA, Canada and China** (see Figure 2 for agglomerated material formulations).

⁴ European Commission, 2018. H2020 Programme AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement – Version 5.1

Figure 2 Agglomerated material formulations in plastic bags

The developed material is used in the production of multi-extrusion boards, panels and decks (see Figure 3 for example), which offer an alternative to wooden planks and pillars in outdoor use, with the core layer containing GFRP waste and the surface layer being primary scrap and recycled material (e.g. recycled HDPE- or PP-plastic from consumer packaging). This new weather resistant composite material is new with no market uptake as so far; however, it's performance will be tested in ECOBULK in various outdoor furniture and structural construction applications, examples of which are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Example of multi-extrusion board with the core being coarse and cascaded material and surface primary scrap and recycled material.

Figure 4 Examples of construction applications of Conenor's multi-extrusion boards and panels created during the project

Conenor's technology is proposed for ETV due to its ability of recycling complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) by manufacturing into new circular raw materials to improve the materials efficiency, as well as their sustainability.

3.3. Results of the eligibility assessment

The Quick Scan document for Conenor's technology was completed in October 2020 to provide the main characteristics of the technology to the ETV Verification Bodies (see Appendix 1), which is a starting point of the verification process. The evaluation run by Eurofins Expert Services Oy came to the conclusion that **the technology was eligible to ETV.**

4. Valorisation of Conenor's solution

4.1. Issue: recycling end of life wind blades

The lifetime of a wind turbine is around 20 to 30 years.

The oil crisis in 1973 rekindled interest in large-scale wind power so the first wind farms appeared in the USA and in Europe in the 1970's. The first large European wind turbine was built in Tvind, Denmark, in 1975 and it is still running and producing electricity for a school.

Nowadays, wind energy represents 16% of the European energy demand.

Figure 5: European wind energy generation, 2020 (Source: WindEurope)

85-90% of the total mass of a wind turbine can be recycled because most of the components – including steel, cement, copper wire, electronics and gearing – have established recycling circles. However, **wind turbine blades are more challenging to recycle**. They contain complex composite materials – a combination of reinforced fibres (usually glass or carbon fibres) and a matrix made of thermosets, typically either polyester or epoxy.

Only four countries in Europe have banned the disposal of wind turbine blades: Germany, Austria, the Netherlands and Finland. In France, from 1 July 2022, at least 90% of the weight of dismantled wind turbines must be reused or recycled, including at least 35% for the most complex part to recycle, i.e. the rotors, i.e. the part above the mast, consisting of the nacelle and the blades. And the requirements will rise rapidly: 95% of the total weight in 2024 and up to 55% of the rotors in 2025.

WindEurope released a position paper in June 2021, calling for a Europe-wide landfill ban on decommissioned wind turbine blades by 2025.

The number of blades that have been decommissioned so far remains low. But it will increase over the coming years. WindEurope expects around 25,000 tonnes of blades to reach the end of their operational life annually by 2025 and the annual decommissioned volume could double to **52,000 tonnes by 2030**.

Conenor's technology offers another new and innovative solution to tackle the issue of recycling wind turbine blades made of complex composite materials. ETV was one solution to bring to the fore the technology developed by the company. Environmental Production Declaration is another way to communicate on the Environmental Performance of the final product.

4.2. LCA results and potential comparisons

4.2.1. LCA results of CONENOR's material

Within the deliverable D7.2, a Life Cycle Assessment was performed on one composition of the material developed by Conenor.

The whole results are available in D7.2 and the main results are recalled here.

Table 2: LCA results for 1kg of composite

Impact category	Unit	Total	A1 & A2	A3	A4 & A5	C & D
Total global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	2,7E+00	1,7E-01	7,0E-01	5,5E-02	1,8E+00
Fossil global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	3,1E+00	6,0E-01	6,6E-01	5,5E-02	1,8E+00
Biogenic global warming (GWP100)	kg CO2 eq	-4,0E-01	-4,3E-01	4,5E-02	4,1E-05	-1,1E-02
Carbon dioxide storage	kg CO2 eq	-4,0E-01	-4,4E-01	4,5E-02	4,0E-05	-1,1E-02
Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	9,9E-08	7,8E-08	6,3E-08	9,9E-09	-5,2E-08
Acidification	kg SO2 eq	2,0E-03	2,1E-03	1,2E-03	1,4E-04	-1,5E-03
Eutrophication	kg PO4--- eq	6,0E-04	4,3E-04	1,6E-04	2,3E-05	-1,7E-05
Photochemical oxidation	kg C2H4 eq	1,3E-04	1,5E-04	5,0E-05	5,2E-06	-8,2E-05
Abiotic depletion, non fossil ressources	kg Sb eq	2,5E-07	1,6E-07	8,1E-08	2,3E-09	1,6E-08
Abiotic depletion, fossil ressources	MJ	1,4E+01	1,8E+01	4,2E+00	8,1E-01	-8,7E+00
Renewable energy	MJ	5,6E+00	5,0E+00	9,6E-01	1,1E-03	-3,9E-01
Non renewable energy	MJ	1,6E+01	1,9E+01	5,6E+00	8,2E-01	-1,0E+01
Use of secondary material	kg	4,7E-01	4,7E-01	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Use of renewable secondary fuels	MJ	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Use of non renewable secondary fuels	MJ	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Net use of fresh water	m3	1,3E-02	5,8E-03	4,1E-03	1,4E-06	2,9E-03
Hazardous waste disposed	kg	1,5E-01	1,0E-02	9,0E-02	2,5E-05	5,1E-02
Non hazardous waste disposed	kg	6,0E-02	9,7E-02	6,7E-02	2,7E-04	-1,1E-01
Radioactive waste disposed	kg	6,1E-05	5,2E-05	3,5E-05	5,6E-06	-3,2E-05
Components for reuse	kg	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Materials for recycling	kg	2,3E-06	2,3E-06	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00

Materials for energy recovery	kg	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Exported heat	MJ	6,2E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	4,7E-04	6,2E+00
Exported electricity	kWh	3,0E-01	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	2,3E-05	3,0E-01
CML abiotic depletion 2002	kg Sb eq	6,6E-03	8,5E-03	2,2E-03	3,6E-04	-4,4E-03
ADP, non fossil resources, V1	kg Sb eq	4,7E-07	3,0E-07	1,4E-07	3,8E-09	3,4E-08
Unspecified input	kg	1,5E-15	1,5E-15	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Air pollution	m3	6,1E+01	5,1E+01	2,1E+01	4,6E+00	-1,6E+01
Water pollution	m3	4,5E-01	2,1E-01	1,8E-01	1,6E-02	5,5E-02
Renewable energy, used as raw mat	MJ	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00
Non renewable energy, used as raw mat	MJ	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00	0,0E+00

4.2.2. EPD for building materials

An Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is an independently verified and registered document that communicates transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. In the field of construction materials and components, the requirements of the standard EN 15804 are used to perform the environmental evaluation.

Specific databases exist to promote EPDs for building materials and components.

According to the expert [Jane Anderson](#), "At the start of January 2021, there are just over 10,000 Verified Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) to EN 15804 for construction products registered globally. In addition, use of concrete EPD generators in the United States means there are now over 36,000 EPD for concrete there, mostly using ISO 21930."

Figure 6: Growth in numbers of Construction Product EPD to EN 15804 (source: ConstructionLCA)

Figure 7: Databases and countries publishing verified EN 15804 EPD (source: ConstructionLCA)

According to ConstructionLCA, **five database provide nearly 80% of the verified EN 15804 EPD**: FDES (France), UL Environment (USA), IBU (Germany), EPD Norge (Norway), International EPD.

Table 3: List of most important EPD databases worldwide

Database name	Geography	Number of registrations (oct.2021)	Website	Organization
INIES	France	3082	www.inies.fr	Alliance HQE-GBC
EPD®	International	1070*	www.environdec.com	EPD International AB (Sweden)
SPOT	USA	1574*	https://spot.ul.com	UL Environment
ÖKOBAUDAT	Germany	944	www.oekobaudat.de	Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (Displays the EPD of IBU)
EPD Norge	Norway	>1500	www.epd-norge.no	EPD Norge

* Source: ConstructionLCA

In the Finish national database [RAKENNUSTIETO](#) there are 174 EPD for construction products that are registered.

Table 4: List of EPD for cladding solutions in main databases

Database name	Cladding products
INIES (France)	207
EPD® (International)	6
SPOT (USA)	3
ÖKOBAUDAT (Germany)	0
EPD Norge (Norway)	0

In the Finish national database [RAKENNUSTIETO](#) there is one cladding reference.

Among the cladding products with a verified EPD, two references are interesting to look at:

- EnviroBuild Hyperion Composite Products (Decking, Cladding, and Fencing), in EPD®

Source: <https://portal.environdec.com/api/api/v1/EPDLibrary/Files/84fe285b-20f2-466c-55dc-08d9149663be/Data>

- Silvadec wood composite cladding slat - Atmospheric cladding, in INIES

Source: <https://www.base-inies.fr/iniesV4/dist/infos-produit>

Hyperion offers innovative ranges of wood-polymer composite (WPC) products, produced by extruding lengths composite material. The Sentinel Cladding range is produced using a composite of 60% FSC® certified wood reclaimed from postindustrial manufacturing and 30% recycled High Density Polyethylene (HDPE). The exact origin of the HDPE is not given but it is claimed to be a 100% post-consumer material coming from China.

For the Silvadec product, there is 7% of HDPE regenerated (25% of the HDPE content), coming from the internal recycling of the scraps of the company. Moreover, it is said that the company offers a take back service of end of life claddings in order to recycle them in their manufacturing process.

Table 5: Comparison of Conenor's composite and other materials with an EPD

Impact category	Unit	Conenor	Silvadec	Hyperion
Climate change	kg eq CO2 / kg / year	2,7	0,73	2,59
<i>Number of years</i>	<i>years</i>	1	40	30
Climate change	kg eq CO2 / kg	2,7	29,1	77,7

! It is important to keep in mind that the comparison is limited to the only climate change indicator and further investigation should be needed to confirm that these materials are really usable for the same functions and that methodologies are strictly equal.

In the context of the project ECOBULK, the results are very favourable for the Conenor composite. The end of life scenario is quite different in the three evaluations: an incineration scenario is taken into account for Conenor whereas landfilling is the scenario used for the Silvadec and Hyperion product. This landfilling scenario is the default scenario chosen by the organization who realized the EPD for the materials of Silvadec and Hyperion. On the contrary, given the information provided by CONENOR, an incineration scenario seems consistent.

5. Conclusions and next steps

Technology proposed for ETV was Conenor's Agglomeration process for manufacturing raw materials from recycled and waste feedstock materials; and extruded single and multilayer products (e.g. planks and panels) thereof for the construction industry. The technology has been proposed for ETV due to its ability of recycling complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) by manufacturing into new circular raw materials to improve the materials efficiency, as well as their sustainability.

The first step of the verification process carried out by EUROFINs came to the conclusion that the solution was eligible to ETV. However, due to

Conenor's technical and financial reasons, the process of ETV didn't move on to the next step.

Nevertheless, Conenor's technology offers another new and innovative solution to tackle the issue of recycling wind turbine blades made of complex composite materials.

An Environmental Product Declaration (EPD) is an independently verified and registered document that communicates transparent and comparable information about the life-cycle environmental impact of products. The analysis of the main worldwide databases for construction products show that there are very few EPD at present dealing with post-consumer recycled materials. In the future, there is an opportunity for CONENOR to develop either a general EPD for a range of similar products, emphasizing on the presence of recycled content and the origin of this content, or individual EPD to show the main difference according to the composition of the composite.

Appendix 1 Quick Scan form

EU Environmental Technology Verification

Quick-Scan

Purpose: This form intends to collect sufficient information about the technology you would like to propose for verification in order to evaluate whether your technology is eligible for verification under the EU ETV Programme and to provide you with a first indication of the costs involved. This Quick Scan is to be completed by the proposer and assessed by the Verification Body. The boxes for responses, in grey, may be extended but the responses should remain brief (no more than one half-page each).

Verification Body	Proposer
Name: Eurofins Expert Services Oy Contact person: Mr. Matti LANU Address: P.O Box 47 FI-02151 ESPOO FINLAND Telephone: +358 400 813 611 Telefax: Email: MattiLanu@eurofins.fi Date Quick Scan:	Name: Conenor Oy Contact person: Markku Vilkki Address: Kaitilantie 30A FI-16300 Orimattila Code NACE: 28990 Number of employees: 1 + hired work force Telephone: +358407534605 Telefax: n/a Email: markku.vilkki@conenor.com

Quick-Scan date: 9.10.2020

Previous Quick Scan performed: No Yes, date:

Indicate if you have already submitted a quick-scan on the same or similar technology to be evaluated by this Verification Body

Identification of the Technology

Name of the Technology: **Agglomeration process for manufacturing raw materials from recycled and waste feedstock materials** (e.g. cured thermoset glass fibre polymer GFRP-waste and thereafter extruded single- and multilayer products e.g. planks and panels made thereof)

NB : A technology can be a product, a process or a service

Technology Area:

Water Treatment and Monitoring

Materials, Waste and Resources

Energy Technologies

Other:

If the technology could fit in more than one area, please signal this and insert a clarification in the comment section.

Comments: Technology includes thermo-mechanical recycling of cured thermoset glass fibre plastic (GFRP) waste e.g. from EoL wind turbine blades and boats and other sources acting as reinforcements in recycled and/or virgin thermoplastic polymer (PE/PP) materials

Market readiness

Is the technology already on the market?

No Yes, number years:

If no, is there a prototype or a demonstration unit available?

No Yes Pilot scale Full-scale

When transforming the prototype/ demonstration unit into a marketable product, will any changes affect the technology's performance?

No reason: only scale-up needed in known bigger volume manufacturing equipment existing in the market

Yes How substantial will the changes be?

A verification will check whether the technology matches the claimed performance. Ideally this verification should only be done once the product is finished, so as to reduce costs of new verifications with changes or upgrades to the technology.

The intention is to determine if the technology is ready to market: "is it available on the market or at least available at a stage where no substantial change affecting its performance will be implemented before introducing the technology on the market (e.g. full-scale or pilot scale with direct and clear scale-up instructions)".

Comments:

General description of the Technology

Introduction or context: Recycling of complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) by manufacturing into new circular thermoplastic PE/PP based raw materials to improve materials efficiency and sustainability. see pitch presentation <http://www.conenor.com/s/Conenor-FRP-waste-processes-mfx6.pdf>

Briefly explain the specific problem(s) or opportunities your technology wishes to address

Glass fiber reinforced thermoset composite (GFRP) is the type of composite most produced in Europe. In 2018, according to the "Composites Market Report 2018" published by AVK and Carbon Composites, its production reached 686.000 tons Europe. In comparison, the demand for carbon fiber composite for any type of matrix material was of 52.500 tons the same year. However, these materials have a major drawback, they are very difficult or better say impossible to recycle. The cured nature of the thermoset polymer prevents this type of composite from being re-melted or reshaped. Considering the significant amount of glass fiber reinforced thermoset composite products being produced every year in Europe, recycling solutions for these products need to be implemented on an industrial and European scale.

How does this technology address the problems or opportunities?

Main purpose of the technology: Complex polymeric waste e.g. fibre reinforced composites (GFRP) and construction & demolition waste (wood, wool insulations) can be easily and at low cost first shredded down mechanically into smaller particle and thereafter used in Conenor invented and patented (Europe, USA, Canada, China pending) technique into new circular raw materials together with recycled post-consumer and -industrial and/or virgin thermoplastics PE and PP.

Especially the rapidly growing wind energy sector has a major environmental problem how to recycle the massive turbine blades sustainably where the European umbrella organization WindEurope as well as lately the president of International Solid Waste Association ISWA have presented their concerns, see <https://windeurope.org/newsroom/news/blade-recycling-a-top-priority-for-the-wind-industry/>

Furthermore on national level the same recycling problem besides of wind energy industry is also present in other GFRP-material using industries like e.g. boating, see in Finland <https://svenska.yle.fi/artikel/2019/12/17/batindustrins-avfall-gravs-fortfarande-ner-ingen-vill-investera-i-atervinningen>

Use of the GFRP-waste in recycled thermoplastic PE/PP polymers is besides of opening a sustainable low-cost technology and solution how to effectively recycle complex cured fibre reinforced thermosets (GFRP/CFRP) also is enhancing the recycling rate and use of common bulk thermoplastics PE and PP in new volume structural applications where the reinforcement effect is needed to allow these materials becoming used.

Relevant alternatives – but not equal material recycling in full

gasification, high voltage fragmentation, co-production in cement kiln, solvolysis, pyrolysis but they all are disposal routes for GFRP-waste, not circular, lower TRL and investment intensive

The 'relevant alternative' helps to determine the environmental advantages and disadvantages of each new technology through a qualitative comparison (quantitative if data is available). It should perform an identical or similar function than the technology under verification but can correspond to different technologies working in sequence, e.g. a sorting procedure including dismantlement can be an alternative to a crusher. It should refer to a technology that is both current and commercially available, should be legal and accepted by the end-users on the specific targeted market, should also be effective in achieving a high general level of protection of the environment as a whole.

Principle used: Agglomeration in the following process steps at semi-molting stage of the matrix polymer PE or PP and additives, see below

An industrial scale agglomeration equipment for commercial use for outputs exceeding 1ton/h with closed loop cooling water circulation and vacuum filtering and extracting of volatiles shown in figures below.

Which are the scientific or technical principles and techniques used by this technology

Which are the main claim(s) on the technology's performance that would need to be verified? (Initial performance claim)

Consider as much as possible verifiable, quantifiable features, expressed in absolute (i.e. not comparative) terms. Please note that the initial performance claim is starting point for the verification and may evolve during the verification process

- utilization of complex “non-recyclable” composite waste typically becoming landfilled or incinerated such as cured thermoset based fibre composites (GFRP/CFRP) up to levels >50%-w. of the total material composition
- total recycled and waste material content can be up to 95%-w. of the total composite material composition with recycled PE and/or PP
- simple continuous batch process with commonly known and existing equipment in the market working at relatively 1. low energy consumption (electrical) and 2. cooling water (not becoming in contact with materials being processed) per produced kg composite material composition
- as the process is parallel removing moisture from the feedstock materials used, there is no need for separate pre-drying those material fractions containing water which is saving energy and costs
- the process can utilise also contaminated waste materials without sorting where only metals and other hard materials have been removed
- depending on alternative sources for feedstock materials and their pricing, certain composite material formulations produced in the process come at as low cost of manufacture as less than 500 Euro/tonne
- performance characters of most composite material formulations produced in the process are adequate for new volume applications (e.g. construction, infrastructure, transportation) where those neat polymeric materials PE/PP are not applicable
- the composite material formulations produced in the process are circular and recyclable more than once back into the same product manufacturing process using simple low cost and low energy consumption grinding process and equipment without significant reduction of key performance properties (depending on product structure and application requirements in full or part of the new material formulation)

Under which conditions is this performance(s) achieved?

Detail the key operational parameters and limits in order for the technology to perform as described in the claim.

- metals, rocks, concrete, sand etc. alike hard and abrasive materials need to be removed from the feedstock materials
- feedstock materials shall be substantially free of biobased and synthetic contaminants like oil, grease, food etc.
- all bulky feedstock products (e.g. for GFRP-waste wind turbine blades, boats, tanks and vessels, construction profiles etc.) as well as thermoplastic products for recycling need to be downsized into shredded smaller particle sized materials at about not longer than 200mm, not wider than 10mm and not thicker than 10mm
- moisture content in feedstock materials shall not exceed 20%-w.
- cooling water temperature shall preferably not exceed 20 deg. C
- recycled thermoplastic materials PE/PP being used have preferably not been continuously exposed to excessive sun light over some 10 years
- depending on target application criteria adequate processing and product performance additives are being used and at proper dosing levels

Main technical standards, regulations or references applicable to this technology:

Are there already standards that cover (parts of) this technology? What would be the main regulations relevant for this technology? Are you aware of any guidelines that would be useful for the verification of this technology?

REFERENCE WORK GROUPS FOR MATERIALS:

CEN/TC 249/WG 11 Plastics recycling

CEN/TC 249/WG 13 Wood Plastics Composites (WPC)

ISO/TC 61/SC 11/WG 11 Wood-plastic composites

REFERENCE STANDARDS FOR MATERIAL FORMULATION CHARACTERIZATION WITH WOOD-PLASTICS:

ISO/WD 20819-2 Plastics — Wood-plastic recycled composites (WPRC) — Part 2: Test methods (under development)

EN 15534-1:2014+A1:2017 - Composites made from cellulose-based materials and thermoplastics (usually called wood-polymer composites (WPC) or natural fibre composites (NFC)). Test methods for characterisation of compounds and products

CEN/TS 15534-2:2007 - Wood-plastics composites (WPC) - Part 2: Characterisation of WPC materials

Innovation level

Description of the innovation provided by the technology, in comparison with relevant alternatives on the market:

Novelty presented by the technology in terms of design, raw materials involved, production process, use, recyclability or final disposal, when compared with the alternatives identified above

Simple, patented, low cost (both CAPEX and OPEX) unique novel technology to convert GFRP-waste in minimal sorting and energy consumption with recycled and/or virgin common thermoplastic PE/PP into new reinforced circular composite raw materials for volume industry products (e.g. construction, infrastructure, transportation and furniture) with commonly existing and available equipment, all production waste can be re-manufactured back to products i.e. zero material waste process.

Raw materials up to 95% from recycled and waste origin depending on targeted product performance and application criteria. Final disposal after optional re-manufacturing by incineration where >70%-w. of materials providing energy recovery.

In the whole world there is not existing more competitive sustainable technology to recycle GFRP/CFRP-waste to respond to the existing and ever increasing environmental problem. Other like pyrolysis and solvolysis are investment incentive recovery techniques at lower TRL with high energy consumption, producing complex chemical waste and far from being as environmentally friendly as Conenor invented technique.

There is only one technique and company in the world to compare with and it is with Global Fiberglass Solutions Inc. in the USA, see <https://www.globalfiberglassinc.com/>

However, what GFS is doing in the USA is merely downsizing wind blades in shredding operation for disposal routes like in Europe companies e.g. Roth and Neocomp in Germany are doing. In the shredding process obviously some fine glassy dust is generated as side product in minor relative quantities (maybe <5%-w. of the total mass) and separated from the main stream becoming disposed. This glassy dust is used by GFS in conventional plastic compounding process in ratios about 50/50 together with thermoplastic polymers PE/PP to produce granules for sales. The difference is found there that GFS is utilising just a tiny meaningless fraction of the GFRP-waste quantity derived from the blade waste in dust form where Conenor technique is using all of it in shredded particles (which are disposed by GFS) and also the dust !

Environmental added-value

Please provide a short overview of the major positive and negative environmental aspects resulting from your technology in each of the four main life-cycle stages identified below:

- sustainable, circular and material resource efficient and low energy consumption volume recycling technology for complex cured thermoset based glass- and carbon reinforced GFRP/CFRP-waste first time ever in the world
- resolving the need of landfilling or incineration of GFRP/CFRP-waste seen ahead in coming years globally from various industries and wind energy expansion in particular – there cannot be Green Deal with wind energy without resolving now the existing recycling problem of the blades !

- promoting further wider use of recycled and waste plastics such as PE and PP in recycled composites in new volume application areas earlier not accessible for these materials
- new recycled composite materials being the outcome from the Conenor invented novel process are long lasting over decades, maintenance free and recyclable and reducing CO2 emissions vs. incineration of the waste
- positive LCA result by RINA/Italy existing on similar Conenor processing technique from earlier H2020-project HISER <http://www.hiserproject.eu/> using construction & demolition waste with PE and PP
- besides of providing a sustainable recycling solution for EoL waste in GFRP/CFRP, it is also the solution for the manufacturing industry waste of these materials which today becomes mostly landfilled in Europe though it has been banned by EU legislation already 2016

You are expected to provide as much information as possible, especially for the manufacturing and use phases. Qualitative or quantitative information may be given on emissions, waste streams, consumption or use of raw materials, energy and water. The information provided will help the Verification Body assess whether ETV is the best tool for you. If you have no detailed information you are encouraged to provide any generic information you may have useful to the evaluation.

In some cases you may limit the amount of information, in particular when:

- the technology will lead to environmental pressures/impacts that are not significantly different than those of the relevant alternative*
- those environmental pressures/impacts are negligible compared to those of the other phases*
- the information cannot be obtained – please provide a short justification in this case*

Natural resources (raw materials, energy) extraction and transformation phase:

Is this stage under your direct control? Yes No

Do you have information concerning environmental aspects for this stage? Yes No Partial

In terms of environmental performance, are there significant differences in this stage between your technology and relevant alternatives?

Yes No

Major positive and negative environmental aspects: See the technology description

Extraction, refining, processing, transformation and transport of natural resources including every aspect of all activities involved before the manufacture of the technology's equipment, sub-assemblies or products. By definition, this also includes all of the raw materials, the energy and water used and all waste or emissions released to the environment during these activities.

Manufacturing phase:

Is this stage under your direct control? Yes No

Do you have information concerning environmental aspects for this stage? Yes No Partial

In terms of environmental performance, are there significant differences in this stage between your technology and relevant alternatives?

Yes No

Major positive and negative environmental aspects:

There are really no equal relevant alternatives in the market.

A recovery method called "co-processing in cement kiln" is an option for disposal but not recycling as presented at Suchem White Paper (see below) which is not promoting full material resource efficiency as Conenor method. Furthermore cement is not circular product, manufacturing process consuming a lot energy and in incineration of GFRP/CFRP environmentally harmful gases are generated. <http://www.suschem.org/publications>

Manufacturing of parts, components, machinery and of products including every aspect of the production of the technology. In general, it is expected that this will include the production of most if not all sub-assemblies. This also includes all of the water, energy and consumables used, together with all of the emissions and all of the products and wastes. This will generally occur on production sites under control of the proposer.

Use phase:

Is this stage under your direct control? Yes No

Do you have information concerning environmental aspects for this stage? Yes No Partial

In terms of environmental performance, are there significant differences in this stage between your technology and relevant alternatives?

Yes No

Major positive and negative environmental aspects:

Use and maintenance phase of a product, a process or a service including estimates of its use by the client/end-user refers to consumables, maintenance, and all raw materials, energy and water used for its functioning, as well as all the emissions, products and waste streams.

End of life phase:

Is this stage under your direct control? Yes No

Do you have information concerning environmental aspects for this stage? Yes No

In terms of environmental performance, are there significant differences in this stage between your technology and relevant alternatives?

Yes No

Major positive and negative environmental aspects:

End of life of a technology including every aspect of all activities involved in the 'End of Life' of a product or an equipment, when it is discarded by the client/end-user, including its recycling, dismantling and/or disposal of all components. This also includes all of the water, energy and consumables used, together with all types of emissions, all of the products and wastes.

Potential to meet user needs

Does the technology have the potential to meet user needs?

Yes No

What specific user needs is the technology addressing? How does this technology meet the user needs?

Does this technology address a need in the market? Are the advantages provided a real advantage to the user? If the technology is already on the market provide general information on its success in addressing user needs.

Products manufactured with the patented agglomeration technique are recyclable, does not absorb moisture, does not swell nor promote bacteria growth, maintains original properties in use, does not split nor splinter, no harmful substances to environment (e.g. formaldehyde), no leaching, can be worked with normal standard tools in the field and in all weather conditions, colored online thus no need for painting or maintenance

Large scale demonstrations are being constructed in 4y. H2020-project Ecobulk www.ecobulk.eu in Finland, UK, France and Portugal where Conenor has produced and supplied several tons of recycled composite materials.

The technology was participating this award competition “EGP’s Sustainable Challenge: New Life for Wind Turbines Opened on Wednesday, 12 December 2018” by one the world largest wind farm owners Enel Green Power (EGP) with winning outcome, see email received 20.5.2019 from the organizer InnoCentive copied below <https://openinnovability.enel.com/projects/Recycle-and-reuse-of-wind-turbine-blades>

ma 20.5.2019 19.35

- Markku Vilkki;
- ENEL Open Innovability Challenges <enelopeninnovabilitychallenges@innocentive.com>

Dear Markku,

It gives me great pleasure to let you know that the review of your submission *Reinforced thermoplastic material from GFRP-waste* to the Enel Open Innovability Challenge *Recycle and Reuse of Wind Turbine Blades* led to a favorable evaluation. You will be awarded \$10,000!

AN IMPORTANT NOTE: The final award for this Challenge is contingent upon satisfactory completion of the verification process. A member of InnoCentive's operations team will be in touch with you shortly to assist you through the verification, solution transfer and payment processes.

Congratulations, and thank you for your participation on this Enel Open Innovability Challenge!

Sincerely,
Renato

Renato Vasconcelos, *PhD*
Senior Principal, Challenge Design and Development
[InnoCentive](#)

Fulfilment of legal requirements

What is the target market for this technology?

EU Specific country/countries:

Other: primarily USA, Canada and China, India, Korea, Japan

Does the technology fulfil the legal requirements in the targeted market(s)?

Yes No

Comments: ?

no information available on legal requirements in target markets

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

Are you the sole and full owner of the technology? Yes No

If no, do you detain intellectual property or other rights on the technology?

Yes

Description of the license or other contractual arrangement giving you the legal right to ask for the technology to be subject to a verification procedure:

not existing yet at the moment...

No

Are there any Intellectual Property issues in respect of this technology or any part or aspect of the technology that might prevent its development and/or which could result in any legal or other issues for the ETV Programme?

Yes No

Comments: the applicant is not aware such existing

Existing test results

Are there available test results to back-up the technology's performance?

Yes

No

Please include in our comments, if a test plan was followed, if standard methods were used, if testing was done by accredited testing bodies, i.e. ISO 17025 or ISO 9001.

Comments:

initial material and product test reports from CNR/Italy, UEF and Muovipoli in Finland

additional product testing ongoing in the UK at Warwick University

physical large scale structural assemblies e.g. outdoor benches, shelters, cabins using such products are being installed in project Ecobulk www.ecobulk.eu demonstrations in Finland (KymiRing), UK (3 universities), France (FCBA) and Portugal (Lipor)

If test results are not available, please indicate if you have a test plan prepared and/or if there are test methods available, including standard methods.

Assessment of Quick-scan (for the Verification Body)

Assessment of the technology description

The technology fits within the scope of the EU ETV programme? Yes No

Comments:

Description/principles clear? Yes No

Comments:

Clear and verifiable performance claim(s)? Yes No

Comments: Some modifications may be done

Ready-to-market? Yes No

Comments: Pilot scale available

Prototype in advanced stage of development? Yes No

Comments:

Technology shows innovative characteristics? Yes No

Comments:

Potential to meet user needs? Yes No

Comments:

Fulfilling legal requirements (limited to VB's expertise)? Yes No

Comments:

Technology shows environmental benefits? Yes No

Comments:

Life-cycle aspects described? Yes No

Comments:

Test results are available? Yes No

Comments: Preliminary results are available

Further testing would/could be necessary? Yes No

Comments:

Conclusions of quick scan by the Verification Body

Enough information is provided to conclude? Yes No

If no, indicate the information that needs to be provided:

If yes, is the technology recommended for ETV? Yes No

Why? Novel and address to a problem having environmental impact

Technology in the scope of VB ? Yes No

Comments / remarks / recommendations:

Estimated cost range for a verification:

To be negotiated with the proposer.

Proposer: Conenor Ot
Name: Markku Vilkki
Date: 9.10.2020
Signature:

Verification body: Eurofins Expert Services Oy
Name: Matti Lanu
Date: 9.10.2020
Signature:

